
Evaluation of Some Elemental, Bioactive Compounds and Proximate Composition of Three Commonly Used Herbal Plants in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria

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Abstract Three commonly used herbal plants (*B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense*, and *Z. leprieurii*) were assayed for some elemental, proximate and phytochemical compositions with a view of using these findings to validate their acclaimed ethnomedicinal usage. The elemental analysis was done using atomic absorption spectroscopy, while proximate composition and phytochemical analysis were done by methods of Association of Analytical Chemist (AOAC). The elemental compositions of these plant samples in mg/100g are Na: 0.04 ± 0.04 , 0.02 ± 0.01 , 0.36 ± 0.15 , K: 0.05 ± 0.01 , $0.11 \pm .01$, 0.74 ± 0.25 , Mg: 0.12 ± 0.03 , 0.12 ± 0.011 , 0.03 ± 0.00 ; Ca: 0.34 ± 0.02 , 1.20 ± 0.02 , 2.10 ± 0.92 ; Fe: 1.88 ± 0.10 , 0.07 ± 0.01 , 0.00 ; Zn: 5.27 ± 0.28 , 0.02 ± 0.00 , 0.00 accordingly as above. The proximate composition of the plant samples in % are moisture: 93.57 ± 0.04 , 8.50 ± 0.14 , 6.20 ± 0.40 ; ash content: 1.33 ± 0.02 , 4.43 ± 0.04 , 3.91 ± 0.08 ; protein: 0.97 ± 0.03 , 9.74 ± 0.10 , 2.21 ± 0.05 ; carbohydrate: 0.71 ± 0.03 , 50.60 ± 1.10 , 27.89 ± 2.25 ; lipids: 0.23 ± 0.03 , 14.64 ± 0.53 , 6.31 ± 0.15 and fibre content as 3.68 ± 0.03 , 12.32 ± 0.94 , 52.63 ± 1.33 ; caloric values in Kcal/100g are 8.79, 1559.61 and 740.56 according to the order *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense*, and *Z. leprieurii*. The phytochemicals assayed for in mg/100g indicated the following in the order of *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense*, and *Z. leprieurii* as alkaloids: 1.57 ± 0.04 , 2.15 ± 0.05 , 1.87 ± 0.04 ; tannin: 0.60 ± 0.03 , 3.01 ± 0.04 , 0.96 ± 0.02 ; saponin: 1.87 ± 0.01 , 2.83 ± 0.05 , 3.02 ± 0.11 ; glycosides: 0.00 , 1.64 ± 0.03 , 1.53 ± 0.02 ; steroids: 2.94 ± 0.02 , 2.98 ± 0.06 , 2.73 ± 0.03 ; phenolics: 1.91 ± 0.03 , 1.08 ± 0.01 , 1.76 ± 0.10 and flavonoids as 1.83 ± 0.03 , 0.75 ± 0.01 , 1.66 ± 0.10 . The presence of active pharmacological ingredients in *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense* and *Z. leprieurii* thus justify their ethnomedicinal usage in the prevention, treatment and management of various biochemical, physiological, metabolic and microbial conditions, the low calorific value of 8.79 Kcal/100g of *B. pinnatum* may also help obese patient to come down on their body weight, while the high caloric values of *P. guineense*, and *Z. leprieurii* can serve as good energy source.

Keywords bioactive, *Bryophyllum pinnatum*, proximate composition, *Piper guineense*, *Zanthoxylum leprieurii*

1. Introduction

Individuals are increasingly taken a more active role in their health care and herbal products have emerged as a common choice among self-care therapies [1-2], thus the increased interest in research on herbal formulations and preparations [3-4]. Herbal plants are readily available all year round, cheap, accessible and often with minimal side effects [5-7]. Herbal products contain aerial and underground parts of plants or other plant materials or in

combination, these preparation could either be in the crude or refined state which may include juices, gums, fatty acids and essential oils [8].

In Nigeria, many indigenous plants are used for the treatment and management of various disease conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, rheumatism toothache, and sexual dysfunction, such medicinal plants include *Bryophyllum pinnatum* (Lam) Kurz, *Piper guineense* Schumach & Perr. and *Zanthoxylum leprieurii* Guill. & Perr. etc.

B. pinnatum commonly called air plant, life plant, live forever, miracle plant, resurrection plant and Africa never die belong to the family *Crassulaceae*, it is an erect succulent perennial shrub that grows to about 1.5 m tall, it has a fleshy dark green leaf that are slightly sour and bland tasting [9-10]. Folkloric uses of *B. pinnatum* include treatment of earache, burns, ulcers, diarrhoea [11], antimicrobial and antifungal [12-13], diabetes mellitus [14]. *B. pinnatum* has also been shown to exhibit antileishmanial activity, hepato and nephro protective activities, neuropharmacological and anti-mutagenic properties, uterine contractility [15-17].

P. guineense commonly called climbing pepper belong to the family *Piperaceae*, they are found in the high forest where it cling on trees, it is a slender climber up to 12 m high with prominent nodes and clasping roots, the leaves are elliptic in shape about 15 cm long and 7 cm broad, the flowers are small borne on common stalk as clusters opposite the leaves. The fruits are red but turns black when dry [18]. The leaves are used for the treatment and management respiratory tract infections while the seeds are used as spices, aphrodisiacs in men [6-7], the dry seeds are also used to treat stomach ache, gonorrhoea and as fertility enhancer in women [19].

Z. leprieurii locally called Prickly ash or toothache tree belong to the family *Rutaceae*, it is an aromatic, spiny, thicket forming deciduous shrub or tree. The alternate branches are armed with strong brown prickles about 2-3 cm long, cone shaped with a broad base and are found irregularly throughout the tree [20]. Ethnomedically, it is used in the treatment and management of muscle spasm, varicose vein, Raynaud disease, arthritis, rheumatism, neuralgia, flu, fever, toothache and gum diseases [21].

This study is aimed at investigating the phytochemical, proximate and some mineral composition of the leaves of *B. pinnatum*, dry seeds of *P. guineense* and the stem bark of *Z. leprieurii* with a view of corroborating the acclaimed medicinal benefits of these plants which have played important ethnomedicinal roles across the Niger Delta geo-ecological zone in Nigeria.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Collection and identification of plant samples

The leaves of *B. pinnatum* was harvested fresh from Otor-Udu, Udu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria, the seeds of *P. guineense* and the stem bark of *Z. leprieurii* were bought from a local herb market in Warri, Delta State, Nigeria. All species were identified and confirmed at the Herbarium of the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology of the University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The leaves, seeds and stem bark were thoroughly washed with distilled water to remove debris and other contaminants and air dried until all water molecules were lost and became very dry, the dry leaves, seeds and stem bark were then pulverized with the aid of an electric blender (Blender 462 Nakai, Japan) and transferred into an airtight container for future use.

2.2. Elemental analysis

The elements potassium, sodium, calcium, magnesium, zinc and iron were determined by atomic absorption spectroscopy as described by Shahidi *et al.* [22] and AOAC [23]. 2.0 g each of the plant samples was weighed into three different clean well labeled porcelain crucible and subjected to dry ashing at 550 °C in a muffle furnace and the resultant ash dissolved in 5 ml of HNO₃/HCl/H₂O (1:2:3) and heated gently until all brown fumes disappeared, 5ml of deionized water was then added and heated until the emergence of a colourless solution. This solution was then filtered with Whatman filter paper into a 100 ml volumetric flask and made to mark with deionized water, this solution was used to determine the concentration of each of the metals with the aid of the AAS machine (Perkin Elmer atomic absorption, Model 306).

2.3. Proximate Composition

Proximate composition of the samples were determined using the methods A.O.A.C. [23]

I. Moisture content

1.0 g of each of the samples was put into a clean and dried crucible and weighed, the crucible was placed in an oven and dried for three hours at 105°C, and the samples was then cooled in a desiccator and then re-weighed. The percentage moisture was then calculated by computing the loss in weight on oven drying as a fraction of the initial weight of the sample used and multiplied by 100

$$\% \text{ moisture} = \frac{\text{loss in weight on oven drying (g)}}{\text{initial sample weight (g)}} \times 100$$

II. Ash content

1.0 g each of the oven dried samples were measured and placed in a pre heated, cooled and weighed crucible and then re-weighed (the pre heated crucible was done in a muffle furnace at about 500 °C), and the crucible covered with its lid and transferred into a cold muffle furnace and the temperature was allowed to rise to 500 °C in order for ashing to occur, the ashing process was done for about 3 hours after which the crucible was removed from the furnace and allowed to cool in a desiccator and then re-weighed. The ash content was then computed in percentage as

$$\% \text{ Ash} = \frac{(\text{Ash} + \text{crucible weight}) - (\text{crucible weight})}{\text{oven dry weight}} \times 100$$

III. Crude protein

1.0 g of each the samples was placed in a separate digestion flask and few granules of anti-bumps and about 3.0 g of copper catalyst mixture (96 % anhydrous sodium sulphate, 3.5 % copper sulphate and 0.5 % selenium dioxide) added to each digestion flask, 20 cm³ of concentrated H₂SO₄ was then added and heated on a heating mantle for digestion to occur, a clear solution is an indication of complete digestion. The digest was then filtered and made up to 100 cm³ with distilled water. 20 cm³ of the diluted digest was pipetted into a round bottom flask and used in the distillation step, the round bottom flask was set on a heating mantle and connected using a Liebig condenser to a beaker (receiver flask) containing 20 cm³ of 2 % boric acid with screened methyl red indicator. The condenser was submerged in the boric acid by a Buchner funnel. 30 cm³ of 40 % NaOH was then injected into the flask and distillation of the ammonia formed commences by heating the flask, the distillation was continued until the boric acid solution completely changed from purple to greenish yellow. The boric acid mixture containing the ammonium borate complex formed was then titrated with 0.1N HCl to colourless end point and the titre value noted. The total organic nitrogen was the computed as follows

$$\% \text{ TON} = \frac{\text{titre value} \times \text{total volume of sample}}{1000 \times \text{mass of sample} \times \text{volume of digest distilled}} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ Crude protein} = \% \text{ TON} \times 6.25$$

IV. Crude lipid

3.0 g of each of the oven dried samples was put into a Soxhlet extraction thimble, the thimble was then placed in a 20 cm³ capacity extractor. 100 cm³ round bottom flask was thoroughly washed, oven dried and weighed. 60 cm³ Petroleum ether was then added and mounted on the heating mantle at the same time connected to the extractor with condenser and the extraction process initiated and carried out for 4 hours. At the end of the extraction process the solvent was evaporated and the flask dried in the oven at 60°C, the flask was then cooled and re-weighed and the percentage crude lipid calculated as

$$\% \text{ Lipid} = \frac{\text{weight of flask} + \text{weight of extract}}{\text{oven dry weight of sample}} \times 100$$

V. Total carbohydrate content

1.0 g each of the plant samples was weighed into a separate 250 ml volumetric flask, 10 ml of distilled water was then added followed by 13 ml of 52% Perchloric acid into each flask, the resulting mixtures was then allowed to stand for 20 minutes with occasional shaking for complete hydrolysis, the flask was then

made to mark with distilled water and filtered with Whatman No. 1 filter paper. 10 ml of the filtrate was then made to mark with distilled water, 1 ml of this was then put in a test tube, 5 ml of anthrone was then added and allowed to cool at room temperature, a blank containing 1 ml of distilled water was prepared with dilute glucose solution into each of the test tube as standard. To 1 ml of diluted sample solutions was added 5 ml of freshly prepared anthrone reagent and mixed thoroughly before boiling in a water bath for 12 minutes, and absorbance taken at 630nm.

VI. **Crude fibre**

This was done by calculation of the difference between 100% and the summation of the percentages of protein, carbohydrate, moisture, ash and lipid.

VII. **Calorific value**

The calorific value (Kcal/100g) was calculated using the at water factors of 4, 9 and 4 for protein, fat and carbohydrate respectively [24-26].

2.4 **Phytochemical determinations**

I. **Quantitative estimation of alkaloids**

5.0 g each of the samples was measured into a separate 250 ml beaker, 200 ml of 2 % acetic acid in ethanol was then added and covered and allowed to stand for 4 hours, it was then filtered and the filtrate concentrated by heating in a water bath to drive away about 3/4 of its original volume. Concentrated NH₄OH was then added to the concentrate drop wise until precipitation was completed. The precipitate was then collected by filtration and weighed [27].

II. **Quantitative estimation of flavonoids**

10.0 g each of the samples was extracted with 100 ml of 80 % aqueous methanol and the solution extracted with a Whatman No. 42 filter paper and the filtrate heated over a water bath to dryness and weighed [28].

III. **Quantitative estimation of phenols**

2.0 g each of the plant samples was placed in a Soxhlet extractor and defatted for 2 hours by using 100 ml of diethyl ether. The fat free sample was then boiled with 50 ml of ether for 15 minutes, after which 5 ml was taken into a 50 ml flask and the following reagents added sequentially, 10 ml of distilled water, 2 ml of ammonium hydroxide solution, and 5 ml of concentrated amyl alcohol, the sample was then made to mark with distilled water and left to stand for about 30 minutes for colour development, after which the sample was placed in a spectrophotometer and the absorbance read at 505nm [27].

IV. **Quantitative estimation of saponin**

20.0 g each of the samples was dispersed in 200 ml of 20% ethanol and the suspension heated over a water bath at 55°C for 4 hours with continuous stirring after which the mixtures was filtered and the residue re-extracted with another 200 ml of 20 % ethanol, the combined extract were then concentrated by heating over a water bath at 90°C to give about 40 ml and this was transferred into a 250ml separating funnel followed by the addition of 20 ml diethyl ether and shaken vigorously. The aqueous layer was recovered while the ether layer was discarded and the purification process repeated, and 60 ml of n-butanol added, the combined n-butanol extract were washed twice with 10 ml of 5 % aqueous NaCl and the remaining solution concentrated by heating over a water bath after evaporation the sample was oven dried to a constant weight and the saponin content estimated [27].

$$\text{Saponin} = \frac{\text{weight of extract}}{\text{weight of sample}}$$

V. **Quantitative estimation of tannin**

500 mg each of the samples was weighed into a 100 ml plastic bottle and 50 ml of distilled water was added and shaken with a mechanical shaker for one hour after which the sample was filtered into a 50 ml volumetric flask and made to the mark. 5 ml of the filtrate was pipetted into a tube and then mixed with 3 ml 0.1 M FeCl₃ in 0.1N HCl and 0.008 M potassium ferrocyanide and the absorbance taken with the aid of a spectrophotometer at 120nm wavelength. The absorbance of the prepared blank with developed

colours and a standard prepared using tannic acid to get 100 ppm were equally measured at the same wavelength [29].

2.5. Statistical analysis

The results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation for three independent determinations except for crude fibre which was obtained by simple difference and the calorific value which was obtained by calculation using the Atwater factor as described by Merrill and Watt [24] and Zou *et al.* [26].

3. Results

Elemental analysis of *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense* and *Z. lepreurii* showed that *Z. lepreurii* had the highest level of sodium, potassium and calcium of all three samples while the level of iron and zinc were negligible in *Z. lepreurii*, the levels was however high in *B. pinnatum*. Proximate composition of all samples also indicate varying amount of the different classes of food. All three plant samples also have varying amount of phytochemicals.

Table 1: Mineral Composition of *B. Pinnatum*, *P. Guineense* and *Z. lepreurii* in mg/100g Dry Weight Basis

Mineral	<i>B. Pinnatum</i>	<i>P. Guineense</i>	<i>Z. Lepreurii</i>
Sodium	0.04 \pm 0.01	0.02 \pm 0.01	0.36 \pm 0.15
Potassium	0.05 \pm 0.01	0.11 \pm 0.01	0.74 \pm 0.25
Magnesium	0.12 \pm 0.03	0.12 \pm 0.01	0.03 \pm 0.04
Calcium	0.34 \pm 0.02	1.20 \pm 0.02	2.10 \pm 0.92
Iron	1.88 \pm 0.10	0.07 \pm 0.01	Negligible
Zinc	5.27 \pm 0.28	0.02 \pm 0.00	Negligible

Values are mean of three determinations \pm standard deviation

Table 2: Proximate Composition OF *B. Pinnatum*, *P. Guineense* and *Z. lepreurii* in Percentage

Constituents	<i>B. Pinnatum</i>	<i>P. Guineense</i>	<i>Z. Lepreurii</i>
Moisture	93.57 \pm 0.45	8.50 \pm 0.14	6.20 \pm 0.40
Ash	1.33 \pm 0.02	4.43 \pm 0.04	3.91 \pm 0.08
Protein	0.97 \pm 0.03	9.74 \pm 0.10	2.21 \pm 0.05
Carbohydrate	0.71 \pm 0.03	50.60 \pm 1.10	27.89 \pm 2.25
Lipids	0.23 \pm 0.03	14.64 \pm 0.53	6.31 \pm 0.15
Fibre	3.68 \pm 0.03	12.32 \pm 0.94	52.63 \pm 1.33
Caloric value (Kcal/100g)	8.79	1559.61	740.56

Values are mean of three determinations \pm standard deviation.

Table 3: Phytochemical Composition of *B. Pinnatum*, *P. Guineense* and *Z. lepreurii* in mg/100g Dry Weight Basis

Phytochemical	<i>B. pinnatum</i>	<i>P. guineense</i>	<i>Z. lepreurii</i>
Alkaloid	1.57 \pm 0.04	2.15 \pm 0.05	1.87 \pm 0.04
Tannin	0.60 \pm 0.03	3.01 \pm 0.04	0.96 \pm 0.02
Saponin	1.87 \pm 0.13	2.83 \pm 0.05	3.02 \pm 0.10
Glycosides	Negligible	1.64 \pm 0.03	1.53 \pm 0.02
Steroids	2.94 \pm 0.02	2.98 \pm 0.06	2.73 \pm 0.03
Phenols	1.91 \pm 0.03	1.08 \pm 0.01	1.76 \pm 0.10
Flavonoid	1.82 \pm 0.03	0.75 \pm 0.01	1.66 \pm 0.10

Values are mean of three determinations \pm standard deviation.

4. Discussion

Analysis of *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense* and *Z. leprieurii* reveals that they contains potassium which is the principal base ion of intracellular fluid, sodium which is the main cation of extracellular fluid, together both function to maintain the electrical potential of the nervous system and hence proper functioning of the nerves [30]. Both cations are also very important in the regulation of water and electrolyte balance and of acid/base balance in the body [31]. The results from *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense* and *Z. leprieurii* also indicated the presence of calcium which is an essential constituent of bones and teeth, it is also an important factor for many metabolic processes like nerve function, muscle contraction, maintenance of regular heart beats and blood clotting [31]. Magnesium which is also a constituent of bones and teeth was also detected in varying quantities of *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense* and *Z. leprieurii*, magnesium is needed for the proper functioning of muscles and nervous tissues, it is also a co-factor of many enzymes (kinases) particularly those of glycolysis and many ATP-dependent reactions (oxidative phosphorylation, cell replication, nucleotide metabolism and protein biosynthesis), [31]. Although zinc was negligible in *Z. leprieurii* it was however detected in both samples of *B. pinnatum* and *P. guineense*. The biological function of zinc can be broadly classified into three namely catalytic activity, as it is a co-factor of over 300 enzymes catalyzed reactions [32-34], structural function [32], as over 90% of zinc can be found in bones and teeth [33], and regulatory functions [32-34]. Zinc supplementation at a dose of 5mg/day for two weeks has been reported to exert strong aphrodisiac property [35], its supplementation has also been recommended as an adjunct therapy during the treatment of diarrhea in children [36]. The importance of iron in health and disease was recognized by man from ancient time [37]. It is essential component of all living organism, where it play key role in haemoglobin formation and oxygen transport [37-38]. Thus Proper and appropriate balance of these minerals in the human body can promote disease resistance which may in turn translate into optima functioning of all cells, tissues, organs and systems of the body.

Proximate analysis of the food component of *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense* and *Z. leprieurii* reveals the presence of moisture, ash, protein, lipid, carbohydrate and fibre. Adequate and balance nutrition as depicted by the presence of all major food components in *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense* and *Z. leprieurii* can promote good health and boast immunity against a wide range of diseases [39]. The low calorific value of 8.79 Kcal/100g of *B. pinnatum* may also help obese patient to come down on their body weight.

Phytochemicals are biologically active compounds in plants that are responsible for colour, flavour, disease resistance and protection of the body against a number of biochemical, physiological and metabolic disorders [40-42]. Phytochemical analysis of *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense* and *Z. leprieurii* indicated the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, saponin and tannin in varying amounts.

The alkaloids are molecules that contribute in both producer and consumer chain in nature, and have been associated with medicinal use for centuries, one of their common biological properties is their cytotoxicity [5, 43]. The alkaloids have been reported as possessing analgesic, antispasmodic and antibacterial [5, 44]. Studies have also shown that the alkaloids have anti HIV and anti-parasitic, anti-tumour, antioxidant, anti-genotoxic and hallucinogenic properties [45-46].

Flavonoids consist of a large group of polyphenolic compounds having a benzo- γ -pyrone structure and are ubiquitously present in plants, they are synthesized by phenylpropanoid pathway usually in response to microbial infection [5, 47]. The flavonoids are known to exhibit antimicrobial activity against a wide spectrum of microorganism *in vitro* [48]; and this is due to their ability to complex with extracellular and soluble proteins and to complex with bacteria cell wall [5, 49]. The flavonoids have strong antioxidant action [50] and they often act by suppression of ROS formation either by inhibition of enzymes or by chelating trace elements involved in free radical generation, they may also scavenge ROS or activate regulation or protection of antioxidant defenses [47, 51-52]. Flavonoids protect lipids against oxidative damage and this is largely due to their lower redox potentials flavonoids are thermodynamically able to reduce highly oxidizing free radicals (redox potentials in the range 2.13–1.0V) such as superoxide, peroxy, alkoxy, and hydroxyl radicals by hydrogen atom donation Because of their capacity to chelate metal ions (iron, copper, etc.), flavonoids also inhibit free radical generation [53, 54]. Several flavonoids have been reported to have hepatoprotective activity [55]. Different chronic diseases such as diabetes may lead to development of hepatic clinical manifestations and the flavonoids have been found to play ameliorative functions in

this regards [56-57]. Flavonoids possesses anticancer activities as studies have shown that dietary factors containing fruits and vegetables that are rich in flavonoids have been reported as cancer chemopreventive and antiproliferative agents against different cancer cells like leukemia cells, gastric cancer cell, colon cancer cells human breast cancer cells, human squamous and gliosarcoma cells, ovarian cancer cells etc. [58-61]. The flavonoids are also reported as having anti-inflammatory activity.

Saponin although non-toxic can generate adverse physiological response in animals that consume them, they exhibit cytotoxic effects and growth inhibition against a variety of cells making it to have anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer properties, they also show tumour inhibiting activity in animals [62], it has also been shown to exhibit beneficial cholesterol lowering activity and fungitoxic in action [63], and the ability to precipitate and coagulate red blood cells. The saponins are also known to boast fertility [64]. Saponins have been implicated as possible bioactive agent responsible for the aphrodisiac effects of many plants extract [65-68].

Many tannin molecules have been shown to reduce the mutagenic and carcinogenic activities of most mutagens and carcinogens and this is largely due their antioxidative properties which is important in protecting cellular oxidative damage and lipid peroxidation [64-69]. Tannin also has the capacity to accelerate blood clotting, reduce blood pressure, decrease serum lipid parameters and with strong antimicrobial properties [64, 70].

The sterols associated with aphrodisiac properties [71]. They also protect the prostate from swelling and in combination with saponins influences the immune system positively. The steroids have also been found to possess antimicrobial properties against *herpes* [72].

5. Conclusion

This study has revealed the presence of active pharmacological ingredients in *B. pinnatum*, *P. guineense* and *Z. leprieurii* and hence justify their ethnomedical usage in the prevention, treatment and management of various biochemical, physiological, metabolic and microbial conditions as well as food.

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